

Older people – what can be done?

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Focus: Transportation; Social Inclusion

Age-friendly Communities Framework (WHO initiative)

Initiative: Older residents help to shape place that they live. Local groups, councils, businesses and residents all work together to identify and make changes in both the physical and social environments, (e.g. transport, outdoor spaces, volunteering and employment, leisure and community services).

Age-friendly case study: Improving services for older customers

Isle of Wight's main bus operator has incorporated training into its compulsory programme for all drivers, using an age simulation suit and glasses to give participants insight into common physical challenges in later life.

Delivered over three hours and tailored to each organisation, training covers:

- What age-friendly means
- Changes that happen to us as we get older
- Communication skills
- Bespoke content for the participating organisation

Evaluation:

Since introducing age-friendly training, reduction seen in incidents involving slips, trips and falls. Company achieved 96% overall customer satisfaction rate (Autumn 2017 Bus Passengers Survey), one of highest rates in the country.

Training has led to improved bus services for older customers, including timetable changes so drivers allow passengers more time to board. Even a small change - an extra minute added to a route - can make a difference.

Around 450 bus drivers across 14 companies received age-friendly training. Follow up exploring how to build on the age-friendly approach to improve transport services for passengers with learning difficulties.

More Information: <https://ageing-better.org.uk/stories/improving-services-older-customers>

Focus: Transportation

Older people's experiences of everyday travel in the urban environment: a thematic synthesis of qualitative studies in the United Kingdom

Initiative: Synthesis of United Kingdom-based studies of older people's experiences of travelling in the urban environment. Searched health, social science, age-related and transport-related databases (1998-2017) to find fourteen papers (from 12 studies)

Activities:

- (1) importance of 'getting out'
- (2) Importance of being independent travellers.
- (3) local environments enable/prevent older people from realising valued dimensions of travel
- (4) travel systems enable/prevent older people from realising valued dimensions of travel.

Loss of local amenities and such features as pavement quality, personal safety and aesthetic appearance, were recurrent concerns.

Free modes of travel like walking and bus travel were highly valued, including the social engagement they facilitated.

Evaluation: while reaching destinations matters, the process of travel is experienced and enjoyed for its own sake, with older people describing its contribution to their wellbeing.

More Information: Graham, H. et al. (2020). Older people's experiences of everyday travel in the urban environment: A thematic synthesis of qualitative studies in the United Kingdom. *Ageing & Society*, 40(4), 842-868.
<https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/ageing-and-society/article/older-peoples-experiences-of-everyday-travel-in-the-urban-environment-a-thematic-synthesis-of-qualitative-studies-in-the-united-kingdom/601B6DDA637125B56085C0B60B1742A2>

Focus: Digital Inclusion

Digital Inclusion Evidence Review 2018 November 2018 Report
 author: Susan Davidson (Age UK)

Initiative: Data largely from Office for National Statistics and Ofcom, with additional analyses of the *English Longitudinal Study on Ageing*, and the *Understanding Society* survey.

Evaluation: Over 79% of all digital exclusion is in over 65s. A worrying group is past users who no longer use the Internet (we don't know why).

Factors that most strongly explain over 65s not using the internet are:

- Lower income
- Older age
- Living alone
- Mobility challenges
- Problems with memory or ability to concentrate (self-rated)

Older people not only less likely than younger people to go online, but more likely to be 'narrower' users, carrying out fewer activities.

Most popular online activities among over 65s are emails and finding information about goods and services. Only around a quarter (27%) of over 65s use social networking, compared to nearly all (96%) internet users age 16 – 24.

More Information: Digital Inclusion Evidence Review 2018

https://www.ageuk.org.uk/globalassets/age-uk/documents/reports-and-publications/age_uk_digital_inclusion_evidence_review_2018.pdf

Focus: Digital Inclusion

I am connected

Initiative: What helps older people achieve digital inclusion?

Analysis of major datasets including Online Centres learner survey and Ofcom's Adults' Media Use & Attitudes Report, with original qualitative research using interviews, focus groups and observations.

Richardson, J. (2018) *I am connected : New approaches to supporting people in later life get online*, Centre for Ageing Better

- Make content relevant rather than abstract; avoid IT jargon (such as 'going online'); focus on activities of interest and on access to essential services.
- Promote self-efficacy – show people they can do it! Make learning flexible and suitably paced; provide one to one support when needed
- Consider if group sessions for older learners may be more successful than mixed age sessions; but without ruling out the potential of intergenerational approaches
- Give ongoing training and support – ensuring knowledge of how to get them - to help people apply newly acquired skills
- Consider importance of physical accessibility and transport; many older people prefer to go to places near home, to not go out after dark, and to avoid bad weather

NB. Older people's fear of digital crime:

- Include training on how people can protect themselves from scams and fraud, and ensure privacy is protected.

Evaluation:

- Success to be measured by non-digital outcomes e.g improved access to information or improved well-being rather than focussing on number of people who attain digital skills.

Focus: Digital Inclusion

New guide to help support residents to do digital in later life

Initiative: Guide produced as part of Greater Manchester digital inclusion ambitions to become one of the first city-regions in the world to equip all under-25s, over-75s and disabled people with the skills, connectivity, and technology to get online. Guide is one way to support more over-75s to participate digitally.

Activities: Guide designed for anyone from **relatives and friends to carers and front-line workers** to help them get started and **support someone** they know to do digital in later life.

Evaluation: May 2022: Not yet evaluated

More Information: <https://www.greatermanchester-ca.gov.uk/news/new-guide-launched-to-help-support-residents-to-do-digital-in-later-life/>
<https://www.greatermanchester-ca.gov.uk/what-we-do/digital/get-online-greater-manchester/greater-manchester-wide-support/doing-digital-in-later-life-a-practical-guide/>

Focus: Faith Groups

On faith, place and health: harnessing the power of faith groups to tackle London's health inequalities. (December 2022)

Initiative: Health Inequalities Action Group (HIAG)

More Information: <https://www.health.org.uk/news-and-comment/newsletter-features/the-power-of-faith-groups-to-tackle-health-inequalities>
https://bishoflondon.org/faithplacehealth_report/

Activities: Recommendations for government, health service, local government and faith leaders and hosted a symposium with senior people in the NHS and local government.

Evaluation:

Recommendations for health services/local authorities

1. Develop budget for remunerated advisory seats for faith leaders on commissioning health boards – e.g., icBs, ccgs, etc
2. ensure all councils have adopted the Faith Covenant code of practice to partner with faith communities in faith-health interventions
3. support the development and integration of an interfaith health Council with national health structures to represent faith communities

Focus: Social Isolation

Community Navigators [Care Network Community Navigator Project - Cambridgeshire and Denbighshire]

Initiative: Informing people about and referring them to relevant activities and services

- Helping people overcome barriers to make use of relevant activities and services
- Identifying where more activities and services are needed and working with local people to provide these
- Targeting people at risk of poor health and wellbeing

Activities:

Examples include:

- Community car scheme for a lift to activities and appointments
- Local friendship club, lunch club or activity group
- Modifications to home or mobility aids
- Financial health check to maximise income
- Help at home support when unwell or with a one-off task

Evaluation:

Data from Ageing Better national evaluation survey and project's own survey demonstrate how the project is helping to improve clients' health and wellbeing, or prevent further decline: 41% of participants have self-reported improvement in their overall quality of life (using the EQ-5d-EL quality of life index) 69% have seen an improvement or no further decline (using the EQ-5d-EL quality of life index) 42% self-report an overall improvement in their health 60% report either an improvement or no further decline 58% report an improvement in their wellbeing (SWEMWBS) 72% report an improvement or no further decline (SWEMWBS) 70% have something to look forward to 52% feel happier; 30% feel more motivated.

More Information:

<https://www.tnlcommunityfund.org.uk/media/insights/documents/Community-Navigators-Report.pdf?mtime=20210330105421&focal=none>

Focus: Social Isolation

The Community Navigator Study

Initiative: Lloyd-Evans B, et al. The Community Navigator Study: Results from a feasibility randomised controlled trial of a programme to reduce loneliness for people with complex anxiety or depression. *PLoS One*. 2020 May 29;15(5):e0233535. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0233535.

Activities:

- Trained Community Navigator provided one-to-one support to participants over a six-month period. Support was tailored to the individual needs of the participant and aimed to help them build social connections and reduce loneliness. Programme delivered through face-to-face meetings between participant and their Community Navigator.

Evaluation:

- Feasibility randomized controlled trial with qualitative evaluation. Forty participants with depression/anxiety using secondary mental health services recruited in London. Randomized to either Community Navigator programme over six months plus routine care versus routine care alone.
- Measures of loneliness, depression, other clinical and social outcomes, and service use collected at the beginning and at six months. The levels of engagement in the program and rates of trial recruitment and retention were assessed. Programme delivery was assessed through session logs completed by Community Navigators.
- Acceptability of programme explored through qualitative interviews with participants, family and friends, program providers, and other involved staff. Programme delivered as intended, with good potential for reducing loneliness and depression and anxiety.
- Definitive, multi-site randomized controlled trial recommended to evaluate effectiveness and cost-effectiveness of programme.
- More information: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC7259554/>

Focus: Social Isolation

Mentors promoting creative and social activity

Initiative: The Upstream Healthy Living Centre

Greaves CJ, Farbus L. Effects of creative and social activity on the health and well-being of socially isolated older people: outcomes from a multi-method observational study. *J R Soc Promot Health*. 2006 May;126(3):134-42. doi: 10.1177/1466424006064303.

Activities:

Mentors delivered individually-tailored activities, with support tailing off over time. Activity-based interventions are provided, with visits from mentors initially on a weekly basis, and regular telephone contact, reduced as participants become more confident and able.

Activities include painting, print making, creative writing, reminiscence/living history, Tai Chi, movement/gentle exercise, computing, pottery, exploring sound and music, various craft work activities, quilting, falls awareness education, singing, hand bells, Walk and Talk groups, cookery, book clubs, and hearing school children read.

Evaluation:

Mentoring successful in getting 80% of referrals engaged in some form of activity.

At 6 months, significant improvements in mental health and depression, but not in perceived physical health or social support. At 12 months, significant improvements in depression and social support and a marginally significant improvement in physical health ($p = 0.06$), but mental improvement was not maintained.

Mentoring well-received by participants. Physical and emotional responses included increased alertness, social activity, self-worth, optimism about life, and positive changes in health behaviour.

Stronger, 'transformational' changes reported by some participants. Individual tailoring and overcoming barriers related to transport and venues key to outcomes. Outcomes achieved by developing a positive group identity and building of confidence/self-efficacy.

More Information:

<https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/pdf/10.1177/1466424006064303>

Focus: Community Mobilisation

Community Mobilisation: Unlocking Potential of Community Power

Initiative: New Local

Independent think tank and network with mission to transform public services and unlock community power.

Home to a network of 70+ councils and other organisations, united in a drive to create sustainable, inclusive and community-powered public services.

Activities:

Building communities into cohesive wholes, with clear objectives and clear plans.

- **How to guide**
- **Poverty Truth Commission** - community commissioners and civic commissioners (e.g. Trafford, Greater Manchester)
- **Strategy and leadership**

Evaluation:

Cahill-Ripley, A. and Graham, L.D., 2021. Using Community-Based Truth Commissions to Address Poverty and Related Economic, Social and Cultural Rights Violations: The UK Poverty Truth Commissions as Transformative Justice. *Journal of Human Rights Practice*, 13(2), 225-249.

More Information: <https://www.newlocal.org.uk/publications/community-mobilisation-unlocking-the-potential-of-community-power/>

Focus: Social Isolation

Signposting and navigation services for older people: economic evidence

Initiative: The Essence Project

Economics of Social Care Compendium (Essence Summary 4)

Signposting and navigation services for older people: economic evidence

A Bauer, D McDaid, Michela Tinelli, Danielle Guy

Activities:

Signposting and navigation services available in many areas, e.g. GP surgeries, shopping centres and libraries. Some services even proactively identify and liaise with potentially isolated older individuals.

Signposting and navigation services can increase access to statutory and voluntary sector activities and support. They can benefit the mental wellbeing and independence of older people.

Evaluation:

Economic studies suggest that signposting and navigation services offer potential to achieve positive return on investments

However, evidence is restricted to a few small-scale studies and modelling. Further research is needed to test those findings which probably vary between different populations and subgroups of older people.,

More Information: https://essenceproject.uk/wp-content/uploads/2019/08/Essence_4_signposting.pdf

Focus: Life transitions; Digital Exclusion

Designing digital skills interventions for older people

Initiative: Older people with long-term conditions or who are going through life transitions (e.g. bereavement, the onset of illness or impairment, increased caring responsibilities) may benefit from easier access to online health and care support. Internet and digital technologies can play a valuable role in enabling older and disabled people to get more out of life, keep in touch with friends and family, and make life easier.

More Information:

https://www.cvsce.org.uk/sites/cvsce.org.uk/files/Designing%20Digital%20Skills%20interventions%20%20for%20older_people_report%20Good%20Things%20Foundation.pdf

Activities:

Report brings together recommendations for designing digital skills interventions for older people with care and support needs. Draws on insights from two pathfinders, funded by NHS Digital and supported by Good Things Foundation as part of Widening Digital Participation programme.

Pathfinders generated insights on:

- Small system-level changes that embed digital inclusion in social care support.
- Factors influencing digital inclusion within social housing schemes.

Evaluation:

Recommendations build on previous work, including practice-oriented research funded by the Centre for Ageing Better and TalkTalk, and external evaluation of the Thanet pathfinder by University of Sussex.

1. Good Things Foundation and the Centre for Ageing Better, Your Guide to Helping Older People Use the Internet, 2019. https://www.onlinecentresnetwork.org/sites/default/files/a6_your_guide_to_helping_older_people_use_the_internet.pdf
2. Good Things Foundation and TalkTalk: Doing Digital Exclusion with Older People, 2018. <https://www.onlinecentresnetwork.org/resource/doing-digital-inclusion-most-excluded-older-people>.
3. Hiteva, R & Ates, A (2019), "The future is digital. We might as well learn it now": Digital Inclusion Pilot Report, University of Sussex

Focus: Community Champions

Stockport Community Champions

Initiative: Ensure Stockport's communities receive correct and consistent information about wider health and wellbeing issues.

Equip individuals, groups, and organisations with the skills and knowledge they need to enable them to confidently pass on information about wider health and wellbeing.

Ensure insight and views of people and communities are understood and influence messages and plans for wider health and wellbeing.

More Information: <https://www.ageuk.org.uk/stockport/get-involved/stockport-community-champions/>

Activities:

Volunteers help their communities recover from impact of coronavirus (COVID-19) as well as helping to improve people's health and wellbeing through sharing latest information from Public Health and other partners. By finding out what people/communities need for recovery and feeding it back, they help shape future services.

Network of participating organisations collaborates to share knowledge, learning and experience. Code of Conduct developed to underpin how Community Champions work.

Essentials Training programme developed as induction which all Community Champions are required to complete. Training evolves over time based on feedback to anticipate substantial change in government guidance.

Age UK Stockport delivers training to Community Champions. All participants receive a certificate on completion of the training. Opportunities for additional training through Stockport College, Starting Point and through Stockport Council's Learning Pool.

Evaluation: Project collecting monitoring information to measure ongoing effectiveness.

Focus: Coordinated responses

Caught Short

Initiative: In 2017, older person was denied access to a toilet by multiple businesses in Levenshulme, unfortunately leading to incontinence. In direct response to this incident, a local task force convened by Levenshulme Inspire community organisation engaged with local business community to inform them about issues faced by some older people.

Activities: The 'Caught Short' initiative worked with local businesses who later agree to offer use of customer toilets to anyone who asks, regardless of whether they purchase anything from their store. The initiative and supportive businesses were advertised locally via a leaflet. Shops that signed up placed a sticker in their window to inform older people of the offer.

Evaluation: None

Hammond, M & Saunders, N (2021) *A Design For Life: Urban practices for an age-friendly city*. MMU Press, Manchester. https://e-space.mmu.ac.uk/628180/1/ADFL_ebook.pdf

Focus: Coordinated responses

Graffiti Grannies

Initiative: Alongside Caught Short campaign, members of Levenshulme Inspire started media campaign focusing on poor state of walking surfaces in their community.

Activities: Aware that it would cause a media storm, older volunteers from *Levenshulme Inspire* started to draw graffiti around trip hazards along main shopping roads using biodegradable spraypaint.

Evaluation: Subsequent profile of issue led to investments in new drop kerbs and road resurfacing.

Hammond, M & Saunders, N (2021) *A Design For Life: Urban practices for an age-friendly city*. MMU Press, Manchester. https://e-space.mmu.ac.uk/628180/1/ADFL_ebook.pdf

More Information: <https://www.bbc.co.uk/news/uk-englandmanchester-35766883>

Focus: Coordinated responses

Bristol Ageing Better (BAB) Programme

Initiative: Work commissioned out to local partners, taking whole system approach. Harnessed historically strong third sector and within an official commissioning process, a collaborative approach was taken. Organisations encouraged to bid for work with other local partners.

Activities:

- Delivering age-friendly workshops, focusing on age-inclusive work culture, recruitment and retention of older workers, and supporting workers to plan for future.
- Coordinating an Age-friendly Communication & Information Action Group (older residents who help to make information from Age UK, NHS, City Council and others more accessible and inclusive). Co-created easy read guides to services and IT courses and drop-ins. Advised local media on age-friendly language and imagery
- Monthly Challenging Ageism workshops with Older People's Forum, to raise awareness of ageism and age inequality among professionals working with older people
- Creating resources – including in non-English languages – distributed at information points and by volunteers at vaccine booster clinics
- Working with City Council to improve waste services – age-friendly communications about recycling and waste collection, and exploring options to improve infrastructure for blind and partially sighted people

Evaluation:

Multiple project case study design, with focus on co-production involving university researchers and trained older volunteer community researchers. Over 18–24 months of qualitative research across six area-based urban projects (2018-2020).

Five leading themes: mapping and building on assets in highly localised settings; creating governance and direction through steering groups; developing activities with diverse groups of older people; reaching isolated and lonely older people; building local capacity to embed sustainability.

Effectiveness of assets-based approaches in promoting age-friendly agendas depends upon values, skills, capacity and resourcing of delivery agencies, alongside wider public sector investment in communities. Diversity and inequalities amongst older people need to be taken into account. Specific focus on older people needs to be balanced with whole population/intergenerational practice.

Beardmore A et al. Assets-based approaches to developing age friendly communities: learning from the bristol ageing better programme. Working with Older People. 2021 Oct 13;26(1):53–63. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/WWOP-07-2021-0038>

More Information: <https://extranet.who.int/agefriendlyworld/wp-content/uploads/2018/11/Bristol-Age-Friendly-UWE-Evaluation-Report-v02-BR-MJ-KL-edits-090122.pdf>

Focus: Trusted Sources of Advice

Levenshulme Inspire

Initiative: Inspired People (IP) work to meet needs of older people, aged 50+ in Levenshulme/south Gorton. Aims to transform lives of older people living in these areas by bringing them together to become busy, resilient, secure and in control of their lives.

Seeks to deliver friendly, fair and safe service in which volunteers and paid staff support older people, providing activities, social contact, advice and information at Levenshulme Inspire and at activities and events at other local centres.

Activities:

Aims to improve older people's wellbeing by providing trusted information to enable older people to feel confident in decisions about health, finances, care and life choices.

Seeks to give older people tools, confidence and a framework to make their voices heard on service delivery and their local environment by suggesting improvements to public services/physical surroundings to create age-friendly neighbourhood.

Seeks to enable joined up thinking on older people across service providers and enable partnership working. Supports both volunteers and older people by providing volunteers with appropriate resources and support.

Evaluation: *Hammond M, Saunders N. A design for life: Urban practices for an age-friendly city. MMU Press; 2021 Sep 1.; Yarker S, Lang L, Phillipson C, Doran P, Buffel T. COVID-19 and Social Exclusion: Experiences Of Older People Living in Areas Of Multiple Deprivation.*

More Information: <https://www.lev-inspire.org.uk/>

Focus: Access to Services; Digital Inclusion

Better care for older people with mental health needs

Initiative: Mental health hospital patients ready for discharge, are moved to and supported in community setting, where they are assessed in a care home over a six-week period to understand support needed to return home, or a longer-term care setting.

Activities:

- Extra support from mental health social workers, mental health nurses, residential care team, and therapists (e.g. occupational therapists and physiotherapists) depending on need.
- Innovative use of digital technology experts within team to help residents to gain confidence with technology. Digital technologies (e.g. digital smart medicine cabinets and video conferencing) can help improve quality of life.

Evaluation:

Pilot status

More Information: <https://news.lancashire.gov.uk/news/trailblazing-project-offers-better-care-for-older-people-with-mental-health-needs>

Focus: Retirement Villages

Buchanan Green retirement living (Sheffield)

Initiative: 1 and 2 bedroom apartments and bungalows available for people over 60 who are on the Council Housing Register. Those on an Older People's Independent Living with Care scheme may also be eligible.

Activities:

- private residents' lounge
- green outdoor space for growing, gardening and socialising
- communal space for activities that can also be hired for special events
- café with drinks and snacks, full meals and catering for special occasions
- guest flat with ensuite bathroom for family and friends
- wi-fi in communal areas
- communal laundry facilities
- separate indoor storage for mobility scooters with charging facilities

Opportunities to get involved, try different hobbies and make friends. Facilities available to local groups to offer varied activities for residents.

Round the clock care, including:

- caretaking team to keep communal areas clean and safe
- out of hours concierge to provide a point of contact for all visitors
- housing staff to provide advice and support
- care team to provide care as needs change over time

Evaluation: Not yet evaluated

More Information: <https://www.sheffield.gov.uk/housing/buchanan-green-retirement-living>

Focus: Retirement Villages

Peer-Led Wellbeing Interventions in Retirement Living: A Systematic Review

Initiative: Retirement living (RL) communities as setting for peer-leaders to implement or support health and wellbeing interventions.

Activities:

- Activities focusing on physical and mental wellbeing, such as walking groups, physical activity, and nutrition programs, osteoporosis education and exercise, exercise groups focusing on cognitive outcomes and function focused care. In some studies, activities included group education and support sessions and utilized other educational tools, e.g. pamphlets and charts.

Evaluation:

- 7 studies provide emerging evidence that peer-led health and wellbeing programs in RL communities can positively impact both health behaviour (e.g. increased physical activity or nutrition, and health status, e.g. lower blood pressure). Study quality modest to very good, but **only one study did not have a high risk of bias**.
- Peers generally cost-effective, more accessible, and relatable leaders for health interventions that can produce impactful changes. Future studies needed to better understand **how to sustain** promising interventions.

More Information: <https://www.mdpi.com/1660-4601/18/21/11557>

Focus: Community Hubs

Andover Health Hub

Initiative: Located in indoor shopping centre. Joint venture between Test Valley Borough Council, NHS Hampshire and Isle of Wight Integrated Care Board and Andover Primary Care Network, with integrated care at its heart.

Activities:

Initially providing health checks for local residents. Services on offer to expand over time as part of town centre regeneration plans.

Evaluation:

Early data found that:

- Over 1,000 health checks within the first six weeks
- 30% of those were with people from deprived communities
- 'did not attend' rate of 5%, compared with about 20% in other settings
- customers liked hub's accessibility and proximity to shops and other services.

Long term aim to provide preventative and social 'health on the high street' model to reach local people, including hard-to-reach communities. Intended to reduce pressure on town's primary care services, local hospitals and ambulance service.

More information: <https://www.local.gov.uk/case-studies/andover-hampshire-health-checks-town-centre-hub-relieve-pressure-nhs-services#the-impact>

Focus: Community Hubs

Wakefield: providing integrated care from community hubs

Initiative: Connecting Care Hubs - council, NHS and voluntary sector staff work side-by-side to support people in the community and operate from community locations in east and west of the district.

Funded by both Wakefield Council and NHS Wakefield Clinical Commissioning Group, but a wide range of organisations are involved in the partnership including Age UK, Wakefield District Carers and Wakefield District Housing.

Staff working from the Hubs include community nurses, social workers, housing staff and mental health workers.

Activities:

Referrals mainly via GPs, but also received from hospices, district nurses and other health and council staff. Includes people with mobility difficulties or who have had falls through to people recovering from illness.

Evaluation:

Around 4,000 people are helped every year. Aim is to keep frail older people well and out of hospital.

More Information: <https://www.local.gov.uk/case-studies/wakefield-providing-integrated-care-community-hubs>

Focus: Community Hubs

Pooling Together

Initiative: Carnegie Trust undertook series of conversations with communities across the UK, exploring the changing relationship between local government, public services and communities. Coultts P, Ormston H, Pennycook L, Thurman B. *Pooling Together: how community hubs have responded to the COVID-19 emergency*. London: Carnegie Trust. 2020.

Activities:

Community hubs formed critical part of Covid response demonstrating strong leadership, creative practice and partnership working. The Carnegie Trust has identified longer-term role of hubs in recovery from pandemic - connecting people who require support to services that promote individual and community wellbeing.

Evaluation:

Building on learning from four areas (North Ayrshire, Renfrewshire, Lancaster and Scarborough) report offers examples of best practice, challenges, opportunities and learning for the future.

More Information: <https://www.carnegieuktrust.org.uk/publications/pooling-together-how-community-hubs-have-responded-to-the-covid-19-emergency/>

Focus: Befriending Services; Social Isolation

Rely On Me

Initiative: Age UK Darlington befriending and telephone befriending service tackling isolation and loneliness of 240 older people. Service now recognised provider for referrals. Supported by 90 volunteers

Activities:

Provides companionship to isolated older people on a weekly basis (minimum 1.5 hours), either in an individual's home, sheltered accommodation or care home.

Visits involve lively conversation, listening to music, providing companionship watching television, accompanied short walk, shopping trip or for coffee/lunch/afternoon tea. Service aims to provide whatever individual wants from befriending visit.

Volunteers provide driver service to take people shopping and to medical appointments. Visits are accompanied as driver stays with the befriended person until they are ready to go home.

Evaluation: Local Government Association. Combating Loneliness: A guide for local authorities. London: Local Government Association. 2016.

More Information:

https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/418532/loneliness-isolation-report.pdf

Focus: Befriending Services; Social Isolation

Effectiveness of befriending interventions

Initiative: 14 trials (2411 participants) were included; 7 judged at low risk of bias.

Also realist evaluation (of how befriending works)

Activities:

Most trials showed improvement in symptoms associated with befriending but these associations did not reach statistical significance in all trials.

Befriending significantly associated with better patient-reported outcomes across primary measures (standardised mean difference 0.18 (95% CI, -0.002 to 0.36, I²=26%, seven trials)). However, no significant benefit on single outcomes, including depression, quality of life, loneliness ratings, self-esteem measures, social support structures and well-being.

Evaluation: Siette J, et al. Effectiveness of befriending interventions: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *BMJ open*. 2017 Apr 1;7(4):e014304

Moderate quality evidence to support use of befriending for individuals with different physical and mental health conditions.

Overall improvement benefit in patient-reported primary outcomes, although with small effect size. Current evidence base does not allow for firm conclusions on specific outcomes. Future trials should hypothesise a model for precise effects of befriending.

Fakoya OA et al. How do befriending interventions alleviate loneliness and social isolation among older people? A realist evaluation study. *PLoS One*. 2021 Sep 9;16(9):e0256900.

Realist evaluation improves understanding about how and why befriending interventions work. Services should be tailored to the needs of service users and take into consideration mobility, impairments e.g. physical, sensory and/or cognitive, as well as the influence of service characteristics including payment for befrienders, fixed/long-term befriending relationship, one-to-one support and impact of non-verbal communication via face-to-face delivery.

More Information:

https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/418532/loneliness-isolation-report.pdf

Focus: Social Prescribing; Social Isolation

Community Connections Lewisham

Initiative: Social prescribing service run by Age UK for anyone 18+ in the borough.

Supports people's health and well being through helping them discover and access local groups and services

Activities:

Local groups/services include social groups, befriending services and adult education courses. Services offered include person-centred planning support for people with complex needs/barriers with referral to partner organisations when appropriate.

Evaluation: Uses lessons learned to inform development of voluntary/community sector and future recovery plans. Primarily a case study of the London Borough of Lewisham experience, documenting how and why Hub was developed, what it achieved and what is to be celebrated.

Report identifies challenges faced, points to lessons learned, reflects intensity of work and makes recommendations based on analysis of the data.

Shukra, K. 2020. *Learning from the Lewisham COVID-19 Response Hub*. Other. London [Report]; Emmer De Albuquerque Green C, Orellana K, Manthorpe J, Samsi K. *Caring in company: a pre-Covid snapshot of day centres in south London: Report of a mapping exercise of publicly available information from four south London boroughs*. London: NIHR Applied Research Collaboration South London, 2021. 54 p.

More information: <https://communityconnectionslewisham.org/>